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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Pleomorphic carcinoma of the lung is an uncommon and highly aggressive malignancy, classified under sarcomatoid carcinomas according to the World Health Organization. It comprises poorly differentiated non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) components, such as large cell carcinoma or spindle and/or giant cell elements. Due to its rarity, data regarding its clinical course, treatment response, and prognosis remain limited. This tumor type is strongly associated with tobacco exposure and is known for its rapid growth, resistance to conventional therapies, and early distant metastasis, particularly to the brain, bones, adrenal glands, and liver.

Case Presentation: With this case, we aim to highlight the clinical significance of pleomorphic carcinoma, a rare subtype of lung cancer, by emphasizing its potential for early and aggressive metastasis despite being diagnosed at an early stage.

Conclusion: Our objective is to raise awareness among family physicians and general practitioners regarding its presentation, prognosis, and the importance of vigilant follow-up.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Lung cancer, pleomorphic carcinoma, rare tumor

INTRODUCTION

Pleomorphic carcinoma is a rare and aggressive type of lung cancer associated with large cell carcinoma or sarcomatoid carcinoma subtypes. It belongs to the non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) group and accounts for approximately 0.1–0.4% of all lung cancers. It consists of two components: epithelial (adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, or large cell carcinoma) and mesenchymal. This cancer progresses rapidly and has a poor prognosis. It is strongly associated with smoking and has a high tendency to metastasize, especially to the brain, bones, and liver. Pleomorphic carcinoma of the lung is a rare and highly aggressive subtype of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), representing approximately 0.1–0.4% of all primary lung malignancies (Rossi et al., 2003; Travis et al., 2015; Zghal et al., 2024). It is histopathologically characterized by a combination of poorly differentiated epithelial components—such as adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, or large cell carcinoma—and sarcomatoid (spindle or giant cell) elements (Fishback et al., 1994). Due to its biphasic nature, it is classified under sarcomatoid carcinomas by the World Health Organization (World Health Organization Classification of Tumours Editorial Board, 2021). This tumor is most commonly seen in elderly male patients with a history of heavy smoking, and its pathogenesis is strongly linked to tobacco exposure (Mochizuki et al., 2008). Pleomorphic carcinoma exhibits rapid tumor growth, early hematogenous dissemination, and resistance to conventional chemoradiotherapy, contributing to its poor

overall prognosis (Italiano et al., 2010). The most frequent sites of metastasis include the brain, bones, liver, and adrenal glands, often leading to advanced-stage detection even in initially resectable tumors (Kaira et al., 2011). Given its rarity and aggressive clinical course, pleomorphic carcinoma poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Greater awareness among clinicians and pathologists is crucial for timely diagnosis and appropriate management.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 68-year-old male patient presented to the outpatient clinic with chronic cough and minor hemoptysis. A chest X-ray revealed a nodular lesion, and due to his heavy smoking history, he underwent a thoracic computed tomography (CT) scan. The CT showed an irregularly bordered 13x10 mm pulmonary nodule in the medial segment of the right lung's middle lobe (Image -1). A PET-CT scan demonstrated increased FDG accumulation (SUV max: 6.49), with no evidence of lymph node or distant organ metastasis. The patient was referred to thoracic surgery with a preliminary diagnosis of Stage I lung cancer. A right thoracotomy, middle lobectomy, upper lobe wedge resection, and lymph node resection were performed. The pathological diagnosis was reported as pleomorphic carcinoma. The patient, who underwent surgery and was diagnosed with Stage I lung cancer, was placed on a follow-up program every three months due to the absence of an indication for adjuvant chemotherapy. At the three-month follow-up, a PET-CT scan revealed a mass in the right adrenal gland, which was not present in the previous PET-CT and was assessed as compatible with metastasis. Consequently, chemotherapy with Gemcitabine + Cisplatin (DDP) + Paclitaxel was initiated. After two cycles, disease progression was observed. Next-generation sequencing revealed KRAS p.G12D and BRCA2 p.G2078fs mutations, with no approved targeted therapies. Immunohistochemical analysis showed 90% PD-L1 positivity in tumor cells, and treatment with the PD-1 inhibitor nivolumab was initiated.

DISCUSSION

With this case, we aimed to draw attention to pleomorphic carcinoma, a rare and aggressive subtype of non-small cell lung cancer, and its potential for rapid progression even when initially classified as Stage I. Despite being diagnosed at an early stage and treated surgically, the patient developed distant metastasis within a short period, underscoring the unpredictable course and high malignancy potential of this tumor type. Chemotherapy response rates remain low (Vieira et al., 2011). The high mutation burden in PPC suggests potential for targeted therapy, although effective strategies remain limited. High PD-L1 expression has been reported in PPC, supporting the role of immune checkpoint inhibitors in its management (Chang et al., 2011; Kim et al., 2015). Lung cancer remains the most commonly diagnosed and deadliest cancer both worldwide and in our country. However, it is largely preventable. Tobacco use is the leading cause, and public health strategies aimed at reducing smoking rates can significantly decrease incidence and mortality. In this regard, stronger enforcement of tobacco control laws, community-level smoking cessation support programs, and education on the risks of smoking are critical (Cangir et al., 2022). This case also highlights the need to develop and implement national lung cancer screening programs, particularly for high-risk groups such as long-term smokers over the age of 50. Low-dose CT scans have been shown to detect lung cancer at earlier, more treatable stages and reduce mortality (Kızılırmak et al., 2023). With this case, we aimed to draw attention to pleomorphic carcinoma, a rare and aggressive subtype of non-small cell lung cancer, and its potential for rapid progression even when initially classified as Stage I. Despite being diagnosed at an early stage and treated surgically, the patient developed distant metastasis within a short period, underscoring the unpredictable course and high malignancy potential of this tumor type. Chemotherapy response rates remain low (Vieira et al., 2011). The high mutation burden in PPC suggests potential for targeted therapy, although effective strategies remain limited. High PD-L1 expression has been reported in PPC, supporting the role of immune checkpoint inhibitors in its management (Chang et al., 2011; Kim et al., 2015). Lung cancer remains the most commonly diagnosed and deadliest cancer both worldwide and in our country. However, it is largely preventable. Tobacco use is the leading cause, and public health strategies aimed at reducing smoking rates can significantly decrease incidence and mortality. In this regard, stronger enforcement of tobacco control laws, community-level smoking cessation support programs, and education on the risks of smoking are critical (Cangir et al., 2022). This case also highlights the need to develop and implement national lung cancer screening programs, particularly for high-risk groups such as long-term smokers over the age of 50. Low-dose CT scans have been shown to detect lung cancer at earlier, more treatable stages and reduce mortality (Kızılırmak et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

For family physicians, who are often the first point of contact in the healthcare system, this case provides important messages:

- Early recognition of suspicious symptoms (persistent cough, hemoptysis, unexplained weight loss) even in patients without current smoking history is essential.
- Encouraging and guiding patients through smoking cessation should be an integral part of routine care.
- Identifying high-risk individuals (e.g., ex-smokers, those with occupational exposure) and considering referral for low-dose chest CT can be life-saving.
- Awareness of aggressive subtypes like pleomorphic carcinoma can enhance the vigilance required during follow-up of lung cancer survivors. Ultimately, family physicians play a key role not only in early detection but also in prevention and long-term follow-up. By integrating cancer awareness into daily practice, they can contribute significantly to reducing the burden of lung cancer community.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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